

QUAID-I-AZAM UNIVERSITY

DEPARTMENT OF COMPUTER SCIENCES

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August 6, 2022

Authentication and Consent

It is stated that the M.Phil. research work "Image Search Results Exploration Framework" (2017-2019) was conducted by Ms. Maha Saddal (Registration # 020271713014) under the supervision of Dr. Umer Rashid at the Department of Computer Sciences, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan. The research was for purely academic purposes and was reviewed and approved by the Advanced Studies and Research Board (ASRB) of Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan.

The research involves 30 participants (human subjects). The data related to human subjects have been submitted as a reference to the Department of Computer Sciences, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan, research thesis archive. We also want to clarify that the experimentation was conducted at the Department of Computer Sciences, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan, in controlled lab settings, and consent from the participants was taken before the conduct of human studies.

It is further certified that the research paper " An SUI-based approach to explore visual search results cluster-graphs" submitted in PLOS ONE for publication is based on the mentioned research work. The Department of Computer Sciences, Quaid-i-Azam University, Islamabad, Pakistan, has no objection to the public availability of the mentioned research study and its outcomes in the form of experimental results by PLOS ONE.

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